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**MEMORY, SOUND AND CONNECTIONS: GRAPH THEORY AND
SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF AUDIO IN THE STUDY OF COLLECTIVE
MEMORY**

Abstract

This paper presents the concept of using vocal intonation analysis as an important aspect of memory research in anthropology and history. Based on the methods of digital humanistics and the analysis of oral sources, the author offers a new perspective on the role of vocal characteristics in the study, formation and preservation of cultural and individual memory. The article discusses methods for analyzing and interpreting vocal intonations and their relationship to the evolution of the human capacity for cultural transmission of knowledge. The author considers the approach to the study of memory on the basis of network modeling based on the results of spectral and emotional analysis of oral sources, which is based on the representation of memory as a network of connected concepts and information.

Keywords: history, anthropology, collective memory, emotional analysis of audio, Visegrad Group, digital humanities, interdisciplinary synthesis.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada antropologiya va tarixda xotirani o'rganishning muhim jihati sifatida ovoz intonatsiyalarini tahlil qilishdan foydalanish tushunchasi keltirilgan.

Raqamli gumanitar fanlar va og'zaki manbalarni tahlil qilish usullariga asoslanib, muallif madaniy va individual xotirani o'rganish, shakllantirish va saqlashda ovoz xususiyatlarining roliga yangi nuqtai nazarni taklif qiladi. Maqolada vokal intonatsiyalarini tahlil qilish va talqin qilish usullari, shuningdek, bilimlarni madaniy uzatish uchun inson qobiliyatining rivojlanishi bilan bog'liqligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Muallif xotirani bir-biriga bog'liq tushunchalar va ma'lumotlar tarmog'i sifatida tasvirlashga asoslangan og'zaki manbalarni spektral va emotsional tahlil natijalariga asoslangan tarmoq modellashtirishga asoslangan xotirani o'rganishga yondashuvni ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tarix, antropologiya, kollektiv xotira, audioning emotsional tahlili, Visegrad guruhi, raqamli gumanitar fanlar, fanlararo sintez.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена концепция использования анализа голосовых интонаций как важного аспекта исследования памяти в антропологии и истории. Основываясь на методах цифровой гуманитаристики и анализе устных источников, автор предлагает новый взгляд на роль голосовых характеристик в изучении, формировании и сохранении культурной и индивидуальной памяти. В статье рассматриваются методы анализа и интерпретации голосовых интонаций, а также их связь с эволюцией человеческой способности к культурной передаче знаний. Автором рассматривается подход к изучению памяти на основе сетевого моделирования по результатам спектрального и эмоционального анализа устных источников, которое основывается на представлении памяти как сети связанных концептов и информации.

Ключевые слова: история, антропология, коллективная память, эмоциональный анализ аудио, Вишеградская группа, цифровая гуманитаристика, междисциплинарный синтез.

Memory, sound and connections are three seemingly disparate concepts, but a modern methodological approach based on interdisciplinary research using digital

humanities can unite them into a whole and provide a new perspective on the theory of memory studies. The study of memory and knowledge transfer constitutes one of the fundamental tasks of anthropology and history, as memory serves as a key mechanism that allows humans to preserve and transmit information about their culture, traditions, and life experiences. Nevertheless, the study of vocal intonation in the context of anthropological and historical research remains an understudied aspect, despite its potential impact on the understanding of cultural and sociocultural processes. In this study, we draw attention to the importance of analyzing vocal intonations and the role of sound in the preservation and transmission of memory, as well as to the methodological possibilities offered by digital humanities to investigate this aspect in greater depth.

Work in linguistics and psychology shows that vocal intonation can carry "meaning" (Pisoni, D. B., 1993, p.145), "express emotion" (Gussenhoven, C., 2004, p.2) and "convey sociocultural information" (Ohala, J. J., 1984, p.6). This aspect of vocal characteristics influences how information is perceived and remembered. The "age of the person perceiving the information" (Lieberman, M., & Mattingly, I., 1985, p. 29) also plays an important role in the information transfer process. Understanding the role of vocal intonation and age factors in information perception can help us better understand how memory functions in cultural and social contexts.

Human memory is not limited to meaning and information transfer; it is also enriched by sound and voice aspects (timbre, intonation, emotion, etc.). The human voice can carry sociocultural information with different "levels of impact on the interlocutor" (Johnson, A. M., & Brown, C. E., 2020, p. 89), making it more or less memorable and rich in meaning depending on the emotional coloration and timbre. Intonation, rhythm, and timbre of the voice directly affect a person's ability to perceive and retain information.

Voice intonations "play a key role in conveying meaning" (Smith, J., 2018, p. 45) and emotion in speech. They can emphasize important points in stories, accentuate emotional coloring, and even denote sociocultural nuances. These elements not only contribute to better understanding of content, but also create or

reinforce memorable associations. Research on voice characteristics reveals the mechanisms by which sound information becomes part of long-term and cultural memory.

Thus, voice and intonation are important aspects to consider in the study of memory. Their analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of how human societies preserve and transmit knowledge, and is key to expanding our knowledge of the mechanisms of memory functioning in cultural and social contexts, and within individual groups, whether age, national or cultural.

The study of sound and vocal intonation is also of significant importance in the context of anthropological studies of memory. Memory is a function fundamental to human culture and evolution, and understanding how sound elements influence memory formation and retention enhances our ability to analyze this important aspect of human experience.

The role of vocal intonation in message transmission and interpretation has been studied not only in anthropology and linguistics, but also in psychology, sociology, and history (Smith, 2017; Johnson & Brown, 2019). Importantly, vocal intonations carry information about many aspects, including emotional state, sociocultural norms, and kinship, making them key when studying memory in the context of communities and cultures (Garcia, 2020; Martin, 2018).

The study of sound characteristics such as intonation, rhythm and accent can help us understand how information is perceived and stored in memory, but to do so, the issue of creating open repositories of voice archives, for the academic community to access oral sources, needs to be brought into sharp focus. Without sufficiently large data sets, it is not possible to create age- and gender-disaggregated emotional voice models for a single language.

The study of collective memory represents a fundamental aspect in the field of sociocultural research. Collective memory embodies the ability of a community or group to preserve and transmit historical, cultural and social knowledge, experiences and norms across generations. Understanding this phenomenon is key to a deeper analysis of the structure and dynamics of society.

The importance of studying collective memory is expressed in several ways. First, collective memory shapes and sustains the identity and cultural roots of a group or society. Understanding how a particular community remembers and interprets its history and cultural values helps to better understand its collective identity and evolution.

Second, the study of collective memory contributes to a fuller understanding of historical events and their impact on the present and future. Monuments, stories, symbols, and rituals serve as key elements in the preservation and transmission of historical information and legacies.

Third, analyzing collective memory allows us to study the dynamics of change over time and the adaptation of cultural norms and values. This is important for understanding how societies respond to challenges and changes in the world around them while maintaining their uniqueness.

Collective memory represents an integral aspect of cultural, social and historical study (Halbwachs, 1992). This form of memory embodies the accumulated experience, history, and knowledge of a society passed down through generations (Assmann, 1995). The study of collective memory is of outstanding importance for several reasons.

The study of collective memory requires an interdisciplinary approach that incorporates historical, anthropological, sociological, and psychological research methods (Olick & Robbins, 1998). Understanding how communities preserve, transform, and redistribute knowledge and memory can have a lasting impact on sociocultural development.

Network modeling in memory research is a powerful tool for analyzing and visualizing the complex relationships and processes involved in the formation, storage, and reproduction of information in the brain and in society. This network modeling method makes a significant contribution to our understanding of memory as a cognitive phenomenon and opens new perspectives for the study of this important aspect of human experience.

One of the key aspects of network modeling in memory research is the

creation of graph models. In these models, information and memory are represented as nodes and the links between them. Nodes can represent concepts, events, objects, or even individual memories, while links reflect the extent and strength of associations or interactions between them. This allows researchers to visualize complex memory networks and identify key elements in memory, as well as understand how information is organized and accessed. In the same way, the memory network model helps to reveal how communities form their historical identities, which events are most significant, and what connections exist between elements of collective memory.

Network modeling can also help in studying long-term changes in human memory, including degradation of memory networks in neurodegenerative diseases. In this approach, the formation of memories in a family unit may occur in reverse order from second-level memory carriers to the original source, based on the preservation of the individual's basic memory model and subsequent narrative within the sick person's memory structure. Modeling such processes may be important for developing strategies for post-medical treatment and rehabilitation.

The network model is a powerful tool for visualizing and exploring collective memory. Collective memory represents a society's ability to preserve, transmit and create meaning around certain events, identities and historical facts. Visualizing these complex dynamics through network models allows for a better understanding of how a society shapes its identity and cultural heritage.

The advantages of using network models to study collective memory include:

- **Visual representation:** Network visualization makes complex structures and connections in memory more accessible and visible.
- **Importance analysis:** Researchers can identify central elements and key figures that play a role in shaping collective memory.
- **Exploring Dynamics:** Network models can track changes in memory over time and analyze how events and characters influence collective history.
- **Interactivity:** Interactive network models allow users to explore and interact with the data, deepening their understanding of memory processes.

The author realizes the construction of network models of memory based on the results of emotional analysis of audio from interviews in the framework of the study of collective memory in the Visegrad Group (hereinafter V4). The research requires a complex approach and consecutive stages: data collection, systematization and annotation, identification of key emotional aspects in audio, construction of emotion scale, superimposition of time line and emotion scale of audio on transcribed text, construction of network model, analysis and interpretation of results and the model as a whole.

As part of the development of a methodology for spectral and emotional analysis of the voice and the subsequent construction of network models of memory, the author of the study is creating a source base of video and audio interviews. At the moment, the source base of the research includes 3400 interviews, both from existing oral history archives (Institute of Memory in Poland, Institute of Totalitarian Regimes in the Czech Republic, archives of the international organization Memorial, etc.) and interviews collected by the author to create a memory cross-section with 2nd and 3rd generation bearers of collective memory.

All audio sources are transcribed and undergo initial spectral and emotional analysis with the help of a program (created using the Python programming language), which is being developed as part of the study. During the first stages of program development and analysis of the oral sources within the V4 study, one of the most important steps for the subsequent construction of memory models is the scaling of the emotional spectrum for each language from the study region (in this case: Polish, Czech, Slovak and Hungarian).

We would like to dwell separately on a unique approach to analyzing audio interviews using the study of emotions and spectrograms. Emotional analysis of audio allows us to pay attention to the speaker's tone of voice, as it can tell us a lot about the emotional state of the interlocutor. For example, if the speaker sounds agitated, their emotions may be negative, while a calm and even tone may indicate a positive or neutral emotional state. At first glance, this information may seem minor. But on the scale of studying thousands of interviews, this approach opens up

opportunities for us to identify key events and themes in the memory model for each age or for each country individually.

The study of memory as a phenomenon has considerable overlap between history and anthropology, but there are also significant differences in the methods and approaches to this study.

The flexibility of methodology within interdisciplinary research plays a key role in the development of the fields of history, anthropology and digital humanities. Combining these disciplines offers researchers unique opportunities to study human culture, society and history using modern information technologies. This synthesis results in new ways of analyzing data, interpreting cultural phenomena, and modeling historical processes. Methodological flexibility implies that researchers can choose the best tools and approaches to solve specific problems without being limited to the traditional methods of any of the disciplines.

However, differences in contexts and objects of study in the humanities are also significant. For example, historians tend to study memory in a broader historical context, while anthropologists may more actively study it in the context of specific cultural or ethnic groups.

There are differences in theoretical approaches as well. For example, historians may more often use theoretical frameworks related to historical research, such as postmodernism or historical materialism. Whereas anthropologists may resort more to cultural and social theories.

But it is important to understand that modern research based on large data sets should be conducted in such a way that the sources and results of the analysis are accessible and adaptively understandable to the academic community. Then, and only then, will interdisciplinary synthesis be achieved, not only within one approach or method used, but also across a variety of disciplines and fields of knowledge. Keeping data and analyses transparent and accessible encourages researchers from different fields to interact, contribute and enrich the interdisciplinary dialogue. Only in such an environment can a full interdisciplinary synthesis be achieved, contributing to a better understanding of complex phenomena and addressing the

multiple challenges facing our world.

In conclusion, network modelling in memory research is a modern and promising method that deepens our understanding of the cognitive and sociocultural aspects of memory. It allows us to analyze complex relationships and dynamics in memory, visualize information, investigate neurodegradation processes, and has practical implications in various fields, including medicine, education and cultural heritage.

The study of memory in history and anthropology is a multifaceted field of research that unites these two disciplines, but also offers unique methods and approaches to understanding memory processes and their socio-cultural aspects. The combination of some of these methods with modern digital humanities approaches allows the full potential of methodological synthesis in the humanities to be realised through the emergence of high-tech research methods. These methods allow not only the collection and interpretation of statistical data, but also the creation of dynamic models. As in the example of the methodology developed by the author, where sound, memory and digital technologies provide powerful tools for the analysis of collective memory in the Visegrad Group.

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